

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Setting Up a Mirror Site for the Human Reference Atlas

Downloading and hosting the HRA and connecting local data to the atlas

Authors: Elizabeth G. Record¹, Bruce W. Herr, II¹

Approved by: Katy Börner¹ (November 24, 2025)

¹ Department of Intelligent Systems Engineering, Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering, Indiana University, Bloomington, IN 47408, USA.

Introduction

The Human Reference Atlas (HRA) is being compiled by more than 1,000 international and interdisciplinary experts across more than 25 international consortia funded by NIH, the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, the CIFAR MacMillan Multiscale Human program in Canada, and Stiftung Charité in Germany. HRA data mirror sites are being set up around the globe to make the HRA data and code maximally useful for experts and practitioners.

This standard operating procedure (SOP) details the process, or sequence of tasks, for setting up a mirror site and clarifies expectations for the relationship between the global Human Reference Atlas and local HRA sites that agree to serve as data mirrors, replicating HRA data in an alternate location.

The primary audience for this SOP is the individuals involved in setting up data mirror sites and those considering becoming a mirror site. It may also be useful for those interested in how HRA data mirrors work. This SOP assumes basic familiarity with the Human Reference Atlas (<https://humanatlas.io>) (Börner et al. 2021). The References and Resources section contains a more comprehensive list of materials about the Human Reference Atlas.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **HRA Scientific Lead** identifies potential data mirror hosts and facilitates communication between the scientific, technical, and administrative teams.

The **HRA Technical Lead** is responsible for providing data and instructions for hosting a mirror site. They are available to troubleshoot with hosts when setting up or updating a host site. They serve as liaison and main point of contact between the Indiana University team and the team at the host site.

The **HRA Mirror Host** hosts and serves the full collection of digital objects that comprise the Human Reference Atlas, updating the dataset in a timely manner after each release to maintain

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a current copy of the HRA for their communities. They are also encouraged to add and share local data, present their data and code in monthly HRA Working Group meetings, and provide expert input and guidance to the HRA effort.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
HRA Scientific Lead	Katy Börner	katy@iu.edu
HRA Technical Lead	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu
HRA Mirror Host	various	various

Expectations of the Host

Each mirror site hosts and serves the complete collection of digital objects that comprise the Human Reference Atlas (< 10 GB compressed). This includes approximately 1,200 3D reference organs and other digital objects available at <https://humanatlas.io/overview-data>. This is analogous to the way the Human Reference Atlas is shared and maintained on biological ontology portals, such as BioPortal, at <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/HRA> (Börner, Herr II, et al. 2025).

Human Reference Atlas data is continually improved and expanded, and updates are provided via 6-month release cycles. HRA releases are published each June and December, and hosts are expected to update files within 2 weeks of each new release to maintain a current version of the Human Reference Atlas.

Mirror sites are asked to provide usage information for inclusion in the HRA Dashboard in June and December of each year. The dashboard can be found at <https://apps.humanatlas.io/dashboard/usage>.

Mirror sites are encouraged to map local data holdings to the Human Reference Atlas. This additional data must be of high quality and be vetted by experts. Data published in peer-reviewed publications is ideal. It is also important that both data and code are open source. Data added by a host site will need to be accessible via a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license (Creative Commons 2025). Mirror sites are welcome to contribute new code that improves HRA construction and expands HRA data usage. All software code integrated into the main HRA code base must use the MIT Licence with no restrictions on commercial use.

One or more representatives from each mirror site are expected to join the monthly Human Reference Atlas Working Group meetings to present updates on mirror site usage type and volume, progress on mapping local data to the HRA, and provide guidance on HRA development priorities.

In sum, HRA mirror sites are hosted by institutions that have the financial, academic, and administrative capacity to do the following:

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- Download the HRA data (< 10 GB compressed) every six months to ensure the most recent release is available on the mirror site.
- Host all HRA releases on a public website.
- Add local data (e.g., data from single cell experiments) to the HRA.
- Share local data as part of the mirror site using the HRA standard CC BY 4.0 license.
- Ensure that any contributions of HRA code are published under the MIT license.
- At least twice per year, share usage logs with the HRA Technical Lead for inclusion in the HRA Dashboard.
- Attend monthly HRA Working Group meetings, present progress on local data and code additions and download activity every six months, and provide expert input on HRA development priorities.

Private individuals cannot serve as hosts.

Expectations of the Human Reference Atlas

The HRA team will

- Organize monthly HRA Working Group meetings.
- Invite hosts to present in the HRA Working Group.
- Add links for all HRA mirrors to the HRA Portal, which can be found at <https://humanatlas.io>.
- Publish usage statistics provided by mirror sites via the HRA Dashboard at <https://apps.humanatlas.io/dashboard/usage>.

Procedures

Procedures for setting up mirror host sites are evolving and this SOP will be updated as needed.

Setting up a mirror site

- Download the HRA data every six months
 - Download data (e.g., `wget https://cdn.humanatlas.io/hra-kq-releases/hra-kq.v2.2_fudan-mirror.tar.xz`)
 - Uncompress the file (e.g., `tar xf hra-kq.v2.2_fudan-mirror.tar.xz`)
 - Copy the decompressed files to a web server
 - Update the web server configuration to point to the extracted static files
- Host all HRA releases on a public website.
 - Website should be named either *humanatlas.example.com/mirror* or *example.com/humanatlas-mirror*. The first is preferred, but given that it is not always easy to reserve a specific subdomain, the second option is also acceptable.

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- Add local data (e.g., data from single cell experiments) to the HRA using code detailed and provided in the *Scientific Data* paper that describes the Human Reference Atlas Knowledge Graph (Bueckle et al. 2025).

Adding local data holdings to the HRA

Mirror sites are strongly encouraged to share local, HRA-registered data back with the global HRA so the data becomes visible in the Exploration User Interface (EUI), found at <https://apps.humanatlas.io/eui>. Materials are shared with the HRA Technical Lead for incorporation into the HRA. The publication *Human BioMolecular Atlas Program (HuBMAP): 3D Human Reference Atlas Construction and Usage* provides an overview of how datasets are mapped to the Human Reference Atlas using annotation tools that standardize spatial location and ontological terms (Börner, Blood, et al. 2025).

- The Human Reference Atlas is publicly available, so begin by ensuring that the local data holdings do not include any unpublished or sensitive data.
- Register your data using the Registration User Interface (RUI). For more detailed directions, see the relevant SOP at <https://zenodo.org/records/14346543> (Bueckle and Qaurooni Fard 2024).
- Provide a link to additional information such as the original data portal, publication, or the original data. If users click on a dataset listed in the right panel of the Exploration User Interface (EUI), they are redirected to the original data portal or paper. For example, users get redirected to <https://gtexportal.org/home/singleCellOverviewPage> when viewing data provided by the GTEx consortium.
- Present data in ways that preserve privacy of donor information. For example, when sample sizes are small, consider displaying age ranges rather than exact ages to maintain donor privacy and reduce the likelihood that anonymized donor information can be re-identified.

If mirror sites would like to add new digital object types, they need to be approved and merged through the main HRA KG (Caron et al. 2024). Work directly with the HRA Technical Lead for this.

Reviewing data quality

Local data is incorporated into the HRA at the discretion of the Indiana University team. Indiana University reserves the right to prohibit the inclusion of data for any reason. Data that is of low quality, contains sensitive information, or was unethically obtained will not be included.

References and Resources

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Glossary

data mirror: A replication of data wholesale from one site to another site. This can mitigate the risk of loss of data and provides a periodically updated backup of the original data.

Human Reference Atlas Knowledge Graph (HRA KG): The HRA Knowledge Graph (KG) defines and provides the core data structures that are used to store, link, and query HRA data.

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